

Improving Corporate Value With Liquidity, Debt Policy And Investment In The Growing Market

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Abstract

This research examines the impact on improved business value of liquidity, debt policy and investment. This investigation was carried out on the Pakistan stock exchange listed companies with a sample of 100 firms. The findings demonstrate that the value of all samples is positively influenced by liquidity, debt and investment. Liquidity influences low firm value positively, and therefore does not affect high firm value considerably. Debt affects the high firm value positively yet debt influences the low company value negatively.

Introduction

The business value on the subject of corporate finance continues to be an important theme. The major goal of the firm is to raise the value of the business. If the value of the business improves, its shareholders (investors) will raise their earnings, so eventually enhancing the owner's wellbeing. The stock price, stock returns, earnings per share (EPS), the price return (PER) rate and the price to book value can be viewed from the community (the shareholder in this situation) (PBV). Tobin's Q is one index that reflects the business performance from an accounting perspective and has been tested in different senior managers. The firm value is based on Tobin's Q. Tobin's Q is being used to evaluate business performance specifically for the corporate value that demonstrates management performance in corporate assets management. Tobin's Q value reflects an investment opportunity strength of the business (Lang et al, 1989) or its corporate opportunity for development (Tobin and Brainard, 1968; Tobin, 1969).

Its valuation may represent the reality of its stock. Shareholders can therefore determine properly whether they are investing in the capital market. As a result, investments are not lost, while there is still the systemic risk that companies, particularly macroeconomic circumstances, typically impact external forces (Bodie et al. 2008) since they can limit the risk. In terms of external variables of the company, its value also depends on its individual processes or is usually known as core company elements, like liquidity. "Debt Policy (de Jong et al. 2011; Gonzalez 2013) and Capital Decisions (Prombutr et al. 2010; Azmat 2014; Chen et al. 2016; Van Heerden and Van Rensburg 2016). (Golic and Gupta 2014; Hsiao-Fen et al. 2011; Chang et al. 2013; Deventer et al. 2010; Abreu 2016; Aktas et al. 2015)." Liquidity, debt policy and company financial decisions can boost the value of the firm if the circumstances for liquidity are good and the debt policy is accurately linked to requirements and financial decisions.

Companies must be careful about their liquidity. Liquidity is because a company fulfils its short-term commitments as among the most significant aspects (Brigham and Houston 2012). The capacity of the company to fulfil the debt responsibilities should be fulfilled quickly (Brigham and Ehrhardt 2013). Including its cash reserves, mainly from non-fixed assets like money and receivable accounts, the enterprise can satisfy its financial responsibilities. If the company can instantly fulfil its debt responsibilities, it can even be claimed that the company is liquid. On the other hand, if the obligation to be paid back cannot be satisfied, the firm is called illiquid.

When the company has an increased capacity to immediately pay off its debts if its non-fixed assets including such cash and receivables are extended. This showed that the organization can demonstrate its outstanding internal funding capability so that shareholders may believe it. This faith in investors can also have a positive effect on their increased value. "Findings from Chen et al., Van Heerden, Van Rensburg and Azmat (2014) and Prombutr et al. (2010)" show a beneficial impact on the value of liquidities. "Meier et al. (2013), Zangina and Godfred Alufar (2009), Fang et al. (2009), Larrain and Yogo (2008) have reported a negative impact on the

value of liquidity on the company's business value."But companies must be concerned if a company has too much free cash flow since it might generate problems for managers and disputes with agencies (Jensen and Meckling 1976).

The debt ratio is growing one of several techniques utilized to raise the firm's value. One of the systems as a tool in agency theory to restrict management opportunistic conduct increases debt. The added debt may decrease "agency costs" which can boost the value of the company (Jensen and Meckling 1976). The higher the debt, the less unproductive money the supervisor can invest on unnecessary spending. The higher the debt more and more money the enterprise must preserve in order to pay the loan's interest and then also settle the debt's amount. The debt might therefore lower the cost of the agency and also improve the value of the company. The firm may expand its operating cash and profitable business operations due to its liabilities.

Debt is boosting business value by increasing stock prices. Equally, if the company's debt goes down, the bond price will drop. The debt ratio might improve the value of the company, as per Modigliani and Miller (1958), but at a certain stage the chance of loss would arise from the lack of greater indebtedness. To the degree that the tax burden could be reduced by interest payments and reducing debt helps the owner of the company. "Meier et al. (2013), Cassell et al. (2012), Akbar et al. (2013) and González (2013)" study findings propose that liability affects firm value whereas the findings of Jong et al. studies discovered that debt affects business value (2011) specifies that debt has a beneficial effect on company value.

Financial decisions can indeed affect the company's value. Fama (1974) argued that the value of the company was established exclusively by the company's investment choices. As per Fama (1974), the company needs to be courageous to conduct investment operations if it needs to enhance its value. In this situation, investments in the capital assets that influence the value of the company are the investment choices generated by the firm. If the firm spends in buildings, plants, equipment for machines as well as other capital equipment, its value can eventually be developed and increased. "Dewenter et al. (2010), Hsiao-Fen et al. (2011), Chang et al. (2013), Golec and Gupta (2014) and Aktas et al. (2015), and Abreu" carried out research into the impact of financial decisions (2016). The findings demonstrate that investment choices have a beneficial impact on the value of the company.

1.2 Research Gap

Prior to this research there is a lack of studies providing evidence regarding the liquidity, debt policy and investment in certain levels of firm in Pakistani context. There is a significant gap from previous studies depending on the description and results of the research. In the past studies, the company's value was just examined in all samples without dividing into various levels. The research therefore aims to further study the effects of liquidity, debt and investment decisions in Pakistan stock exchange on the level of firm value. Further this study will provide future research directions to the upcoming researchers to better comprehend their study in this area.

1.3 Research Objectives

the main objectives of the study are:

RO1: To find out the effect of liquidity on firm value at a certain level of firms.

RO2: To examine the effect of debt policy on firm value at a certain level of firm,

RO3: To investigate the effect of investment decisions on firm value at a certain level of firm.

1.4 Research Questions

RQ1: What is the effect of liquidity on firm value at a certain level of firm?

RQ2: How debt policy effects the firm value at certain level of firm?

RQ3: In what ways investment decisions effects the firm value at certain level of firm?

Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical background and Hypothesis Development

2.1.1 Liquidity and Level of Firm Value

The theory of the Agency arises from a contradiction between both the agent and the principal as the shareholders of the business. In the theory of the agency the companies are regarded as a system of deals among managers and business shareholders. Managers hired by the owner to run the company often battle among themselves to make greater profits. They often also exploit the power of shareholders such that they exclusively manage the company for their personal advantage and neglect the shareholders' interests or owners (Jensen and Meckling 1976).

In this scenario, agents and leaders also consider the theory of the agency to be a type of game theory which provides a framework of contractual relations among two or more people. In agency theory, the interaction among agents (often called management) and investors or managers is sometimes termed the link among agents and managers (Jensen 1986). In the principal's best interests, the stakeholder or principal anticipates the agent or management to delegate authority to the agent. Executives therefore must take the leading business decisions to improve the shareholders' wealth. You decide to optimize the firm's assets (utilities).

The agency theory also explains the analytical framework based on contractual relationships (Jensen 2003). There are two approaches to prohibit managers from damaging external investors: 1) administrators supervise shareholders outside the company; 2) administrators limit their activities directly (bonding). On the one hand, both methods will lessen the absence of differences so that they can raise the company's value. On the other hand, they both require the expense to diminish the company's value ultimately. While they are monitoring and binding, shareholders will strive to foresee both these costs and the possibilities for leftover losses. The cost of the agency, then, is the sum total, starting with 1) the agreement between both the principle and the agent; 2) the principal's supervision; 3) the agent's bonding; and 4) the losses of residual property.

Liquidity is a key component in the economic operation of the company. The company is able to satisfy its urgent debt obligations (Brigham and Ehrhardt 2013). Therefore, if the company is able to satisfy its debt obligations quickly, the company is considered to be liquid. The company's ability to satisfy its responsibilities leads foreign investments to feel that the company is well positioned, which can build investor confidence. Their confidence then makes them acquire the shares of the company and so can influence the company's value.

Liquidity is a critical aspect in the financial operation of the company. The company can fulfil its urgent debt obligations (Brigham and Ehrhardt 2013). Therefore, if the company is able to fulfil its debt responsibilities instantly, the company is also said to be liquid. The capability of the corporation to fulfil its obligations shows that external shareholders believe that the business is in proper terms and that this situation can generate investors' confidence. Your confidence then makes people are buying the shareholding, so affecting the growth in the value of the business. The proposed hypothesis is:

H1: "Liquidity has a positive impact on the firm value, both on the sample firm as a whole and in firms that have low and high value."

2.1.2 Debt Policy and Level of Firm Value

Financial advisers are using domestic sources of funding to enhance their firm value. The usage is partly due to the inequality of knowledge in relation both to actions and knowledge among people in the industry (Ross 1973). "Chen et al. (2016), Van Heerden and Van Rensburg (2016), Azmat (2014) and Prombutr et al." have conducted research on liquidity influences on the business value (2010). The findings have shown that liquidity affects the value of the company. On the basis of the explanation above, one strategy is indeed to increase the debt ratio. The addition of debt can reduce costs of the agency and improve the value of the organization. The higher the debt, the lesser the unneeded resources can be spent by the management. The higher the debt, the longer the cash company will retain the right to pay interest and pay the loan principal. The debt could therefore lower the cost of the agencies and improve the company's value because the company can raise its operating capital and profitable investment activities by means of the debt.

Brigham and Ehrhardt (2013) highlighted the company's usage of debt by increasing stock values, and also reducing stock market prices by reducing them. Modigliani and Miller (1958) said that the debt ratio may improve the value of the firm, however that at a certain period the default risk would arise from the increasing debt. The lowering of debt helps the business owner, as far as loan repayments can then be used to reduce taxes. Yet, the expense of bankruptcy and probable differential in personal income taxes among earnings from equity and debt will reflect these advantages. Hypothetically, the firm must use the debt that will lessen the cost of the firm's capital.

A good company whose success can indicate a large part of its working capital debt can increase its worth. The value can be increased. However, a lower good company didn't hesitate to employ the heavy debt since bankruptcy is high (Ross, 1977). Study results by Mr. Modigliani and Mr. Gonzales (2013) have shown that debt has a positive impact on company value. Most recent studies have revealed that debt is of a significant outcome on value creation. In comparison, "Meier and Laurin (2013), Cassell et al. (2012), and Akbar et al. (2013) revealed a negative effect on the firm value." Founded on the explanation, the proposed hypothesis is:

H2: "The debt policy has a positive impact on the firm value, both on the sample firm as a whole and on firms with low and high value."

2.1.3 Investment and Level of Firm Value

Investing is the delayed purchasing action to achieve the future value of increased spending. An investment strategy is seen to be efficient if such time arrangements may optimize estimates of utilities. A person or firm will spend just to enhance profitability when the predicted advantage of a consumer deferral is larger than when the money is actually invested (Fama and Miller 1972).

A financial decision has become one of the aspects that might boost value creation. Investment choices alone influence the firm value (Fama 1974). The view that the financial decisions is crucial might be understood. Because expanding the firm value as the objective is indeed to increase the shareholder's wealth created by the financial activity of the organization. The objective of corporate investment decision-making is to achieve high profit levels and avoid risk. The firm's value is predicted to grow in large profits with acceptable dangers. If the investment company can optimize its earnings successfully by utilizing its own resources, it will boost investor capacity to invest in the stock of the company, which has a beneficial effect on the company value-added growth.

Companies' investment decisions are spending in resources or popularly known as capital, such as land or property, constructions and equipment in this research. This research. Investment choices Capital spending is the funds spent by companies for more than one year to improve (Brigham and Ehrhardt, 2013).

If the investment is deemed viable by the company, it actually should concentrate on managing the investment such that it will grow the company's value. The stakeholders will also assess the performance of the initiatives made by the company. If the company's investments materialize, shareholders will react successfully. Similarly, the shareholders would react harshly if the investment truly leads to losses. The findings of "Deventer et al. (2010) Hsiao-Fen et al. (2011), Chang et al. (2013), Golec and Gupta (2014), Aktas et al. (2015) and Abreu are consistent with these findings (2016)." They provided evidence of a positive impact on firm value of investments decisions. Based on the description, the hypothesis proposed is:

H3: "An investment decision positively influences the firm value, both on the sample firm as a whole and on firms with low and high value."

3. Methods

3.1 Sample and Data Collection

This research implemented panel data. The population for this research is the company listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange, while the sample of non-financial companies. This research involve information from the company's 2015 through 2020 financial reports. PSX information gathered and Data (Pakistan Capital Market Directory). Non-financial businesses at the Pakistan Stock Exchange are subject to the sampling criteria in this research that disclose their financial reports regularly from 2015 to 2020. The sample acquired is 100 companies with 500 observations regarding the selection of samples (the number is multiplied by the observing year = 100 businesses x 5 years).

3.2 Regression model

Liquidity, is defined by cash ratio, debt policy, is assessed by debt ratio (DR), as well as investment decision (INV), that is net capital expenditure, are the independent variables. "The cash ratio is calculated by dividing cash and cash equivalents over total liabilities; the debt ratio is calculated by dividing total debt by total assets; while investment is calculated by dividing fixed assets t minus fixed assets t-1 by fixed assets. Land, buildings, equipment and tools are the types of fixed assets in this research." Total assets and size of the business are assessed using the natural logarithm (Ln). Total sales t minus total sales t-1 divided overall sales are assessed by growth. Fixed assets to regulate the impact of variations of firm scale divide cash ratio and investment.

In the meantime, the variable dependant is a firm value. "Tobin's Q measures the company value. The market value of all shares outstanding plus the market value of all debt divided by a replacement cost of all manufacturing capability must be assessed by Tobin Q." Multiple panel regression with common effect model is used for statistical analysis. Three equations are used for the estimated regression framework.

$$Q_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \beta_2 DR_{it} + \beta_3 INV_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (1)$$

$$QLOW_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \beta_2 DR_{it} + \beta_3 INV_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (2)$$

$$QHIGH_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \beta_2 DR_{it} + \beta_3 INV_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 GROWTH_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (3)$$

In this situation, Q (Tobin's Q) is an indicator for firm value as a dependent variable for the entire sample of firms; QLOW is a measure for firm value as a dependent variable for a sample of firms with low firm value, i.e. companies with a Q score below the average size of the underlying sample; QHIGH is an indicator for value of the firm like a dependent variable for a sample of firms with high firm value, i.e. companies with Q values greater than the sample's mean total value; like an independent variable, CR (cash ratio) is a measure for liquidity.

As an independent variable, DR (debt ratio) is a measure for debt policy; as an independent variable, INV is an indicator of investment decisions; also, as control variable, SIZE is an indicator of firm size; as just a control variable, GROWTH is an indicator of firm growth; as such an independent variable, β seems to be the slope constants; ε , is the error term.

3.3 Data Analysis Tools and Techniques

The data will be analysed utilizing regression analysis, which will be calculated and recorded using the statistical program SPSS 24.

The information gathered from a study of previously published literature will be processed and then analysed separately using statistical tools in a careful and professional manner to ensure optimum accuracy and consistency. The collected results will be correlated to one another. Given the existence of the data being collected, graphs and charts will be used.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Results

Depending on sampling selection criteria, the samples collected are 100 businesses across five years and the number of observations is 500 from companies listed on Pakistan stock exchanges that regularly disclose their financial reports from 2015 to 2020. Table 1 shows the variable statistical summary for all samples.

Table 1 Descriptive Results

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Q	0.239	7.320	2.978	2.494
CR	1.021	2.981	1.850	0.825
DR	0.150	2.290	0.851	0.541
INV	0.101	0.911	0.271	0.151
SIZE	1.199	8.499	3.180	1.481
GROWTH	0.111	4.101	2.081	2.221
N	500	500	500	500

“Note: Q (the market value of all outstanding stock plus market value of all debt divided by replacement value of all production capacity) as the dependent variable; CR (cash plus cash equivalents divided by liabilities) DR (total debt divided by total assets) and INV (investment divided by fixed assets) as independent variable, SIZE (Ln total assets) and GROWTH (total sales t minus total sales t-1 divided total sales) as control variable.”

There are two criteria based on the evaluation of companies of low and high company value: (1) when Q's value is less than the average, it is classified as a low firm value and (2) the Q firm is categorized as an endeavour of high firm value over the average value. 280 companies with a low firm value and 220 with a high firm value are samples obtained from the findings of the evaluation. Table 2 shows the explanation of statistics for companies of low and high firm value.

Table 2 Descriptive Results level of firm value

Variable	Low				High			
	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Q	0.241	1.700	1.528	1.352	1.231	7.211	2.871	1.682
CR	1.011	2.871	1.699	0.477	1.049	2.911	2.091	0.451
DR	0.149	2.421	0.801	0.491	0.129	2.259	1.201	0.602
INV	0.101	0.599	0.221	0.110	0.099	0.891	0.411	0.214
SIZE	1.270	2.94	1.672	0.368	2.592	8.561	3.551	0.711
GROWTH	0.111	1.719	1.424	1.121	0.231	4.092	2.071	1.402
N	280	280	280	280	220	220	220	220

“Note: Q (the market value of all outstanding stock plus market value of all debt divided by replacement value of all production capacity) as the dependent variable and to classification low and high firm value, CR (cash plus cash equivalents divided by liabilities) DR (total debt divided by total assets) and INV (investment divided by fixed assets) are independent variables, SIZE (Ln total assets) and GROWTH (total sales t minus total sales t-1 divided total sales) as control variable.”

4.2 Regression Analysis

Table 3 Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.981 ^a	.962	.960	.06271

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, DR, INV, SIZE, GROWTH.

Table 3 highlights the regression analysis results for Improving Corporate Value with Liquidity, Debt Policy and Investment in the Growing Market. It is revealed that liquidity and debt policy generally had substantial link on firm value in Pakistan (R=0.981). Nevertheless, these characteristics explain 96.2% of the variation of the dependent variable that is firm value, based on the adjusted R square value of 0.962

Table 4 ANNOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.885	6	1.648	416.863	.000 ^a
	Residual	.478	121	.004		
	Total	10.364	127			

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, DR, INV, SIZE, GROWTH.

b. Dependent Variable: Firm Value.

The findings of the ANOVA statistics stated above in the table 4 illustrates that the sum of the square value for the regression is 9.885, subsequent the df value of 6. The mean square value is stated as 1.648, tracked by the F-statistics value of 416.863, which is above the value required. Finally, the significant value of p is signified as 0.000, which represents the strong and substantial association among the two variables, such as firm value as well as liquidity.

Table 5 Coefficients

Model		Total sample		Low firm value		High firm value	
		Beta	p-value	Beta	p-value	Beta	p-value
1	(Constant)	0.043		0.960		2.354	
	CR	0.589	0.000	0.391	0.001	0.103	0.727
	DR	0.166	0.297	-0.118	0.981	0.229	0.091
	INV	0.646	0.031	0.291	0.027	1.401	0.03
	SIZE	0.099	0.042	0.043	0.135	0.119	0.221
	GROWTH	0.038	0.501	-0.039	0.176	-0.531	0.047

a. Predictors: (Constant), CR, DR, INV, SIZE, GROWTH.

b. Dependent Variable: FIRM VALUE.

The results of the figures in Table 5 reveal that liquidity positively impacts the company's value itself and the company's small value. If the company has a high amount of liquidity, it will have a high value creation. The results of the study are supporting the studies carried out by "Chen, Van Heerden, van Rensburg, Azmat (2014) and Prombutr et al. (2016). (2010)." In order for the firm to satisfy its debts instantly, the company must be able to retain good liquidity. In this situation, the PSE companies were chosen to select the sample as they can fulfil all commitments, that must be met quickly so that the shareholders can react favourably and ultimately have a great impact on increase in the value of the company. These findings align to the idea of agencies, in which enterprises must utilize their own sources of funding, like cash flow for profitable business, to prevent flow of cash from benefiting management (Jensen and Meckling 1976).

In addition, high liquidity companies are an ever more liquid company. The findings of this study suggest that the companies in the Pakistani developing industry are part of the liquid companies, therefore the investors consider that the Pakistan emergent industry is a sample and can finally improve the value of the company. The study findings show, nevertheless, that liquidity has a favourable effect on high-value companies. Liquidity hence has not helped much to value-added companies. In other words, more alternate factors, like debt, will probably use liquidity at a high firm value.

The findings also reveal that the debt policy influences the firm value for the whole sample in a positive but insignificant way. That indicates that Pakistan's new and emerging market companies can carry out the principle of the agency even if it is not executed as far as possible. The agency theory says one way of integrating processes to debt is to diminish free cash flow via debt, which can also lower management' conduct, which can decrease the company's strategic value (Jensen and Meckling 1976).

The results showed that the sample of PSE companies could not use the debt to maximize its value. Modigliani and Miller (1958) suggested that the debt ratio would raise the company's value, but it would lead to a bankruptcy risk at a certain moment. Pakistan emerging market companies cannot take benefit of their loans for profitable investment opportunities or initiatives; hence the company does not have a big increase in value. "The findings of the study are also supported by studies conducted by Modigliani et al. (1958), Jensen and Mackling, Jensen and Mackling (1976), (Ross, 1977), Jong et al (2013)."

Various results were obtained in high and low-value companies. In short, debt influences high business value positively and substantially. It is consistent with Modigliani and Miller's (1958) assumption that the debt would enhance the company's value. "On the other hand, debt is negative to low corporate value. This illustrates that high value companies are likely to use the loan, whereas low firm values aren't using the debt since the low firm value prefers to use its internal source of financing, like cash flow."

Pakistan developing market company's investment decisions have increased the company's value. This was predicated on the result of this research which show the strong positive influence of investment strategies on the company's value as a whole as well on low- or high-value companies. The research also shows that the value of a company is decided by investment decision-making, as stated by Fama (1974). They can boost its value for the companies investing wisely. They spend in fixed assets like buildings, manufacturing facilities, machinery and many others to grow their business.

It can therefore be claimed that Pakistani emerging-market enterprises' investment selections are proper and would have a significant effect on the development of firm value. The research findings carried out by "Deventer et al. (2010), Hsiao-Fen et al. (2011), Chang and others (2013), Golec and Gupta (2014), Aktas et al. (2015) and Abreu are also provided by this research (2016)." Furthermore, Pakistani emerging-market companies can benefit from the best investment prospects by spending such that the company's value goes up.

5. Conclusions

On the basis of data analysed, one can reach the conclusion: first, the liquidity of all the non-financial firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange and on companies with low values have a significant positive impact on the firm value. The greater the non-financial company's liquidity that become the overall sample, the greater the firm value. In this situation, the low value of businesses usually requires a large amount of liquidity. Yet, high corporate value utilizes little cash flows thus they can't expand their value significantly.

Secondly, the debt policy has a favourable effect on the overall sample, but does not play a significant role. This shows that non-financial liabilities cannot be used to raise corporate value as much as possible. In order to enhance their value, high-value firms apply massive amounts of debt, whereas low-value businesses do not utilize debt, but rather to employ internal finance.

In general, investment decisions affect the firm value in the sample of the business as a whole and of low and high value firms significantly. In other words, the amount invested are right on the goal to grow their firm value in the investment decision-making processes of non-financial companies.

5.1 Future research directions

Additional firms, e.g., all Pakistan Stock Exchange businesses or comparable with some other emerging southeast Asian Countries or Asia, should better be used by future researches.

Furthermore, the study time could be lengthier to receive much observations.

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